

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15735047

A Train-the-Trainer Approach for Implementing Problem-Based Learning Environment in Vocational Technical Education

Dr Wilson Udofia¹ & Caleb, Emmanuel²

¹**Department of Technical Education
Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit**

²**Department of Industrial Technology
University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria**

¹wilsonudofia@yahoo.com, ezekielemmanuel@uniuyo.edu.ng²

ABSTRACT

This study set out to develop a template for integration of problem-based learning (PBL) environment by vocational technical teachers in South South Nigeria. This became essential, given the increasing acceptance of PBL as an essential instructional strategy in technical education. The eagerness to implement PBL is hindered by the skills level of technical teachers' in application of PBL instructional design and delivery principles, of which concept mapping forms an integral part. Instrumentation research design was employed in the study. The area of the study was South-South zone of Nigeria comprising, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers States. The population of the study is 54 respondents, comprising lecturers in the technical/industrial education unit as experts. The sample size for lecturers used in the study is 46. This was arrived at using Taro Yamane's formula and simple random sampling technique was employed to sample lecturers from the participating universities. Data for the study were collected using questionnaire, focus group discussion and the Delphi technique. This went on for a period of 90 working days. The developed instrument was then presented to experts in the Delphi technique, who screened the items to ensure that they served as inputs to education. Seven experts were involved in the Delphi process of validation. Content validation was carried out through the Delphi process. Content experts reviewed the items for inclusion in the develop template. The inputs of the experts was used to build the final version of the PBL-concept map template. The data generated from administering the instrument to the experts was analysed using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR). The developed template for problem selection and PBL implementation was then pretested through a pilot test. This was conducted at the University of Uyo. Student-teachers were asked to rate the training they just received. Cronbach Alpha was then used for determining the internal consistency of the developed template. This gave a coefficient index of 0.87. The study developed a template for integrating concept maps into PBL tutorial. The developed template was validated, pretested and found to be fit for use by technical instructors and students alike. It was recommended that the developed template for concept map integration into PBL tutorial should be adopted by the teachers in the design of PBL instruction in technical education.

Keywords: Development, Validation, Template, PBL-Concept Map Guidelines, Instructional systems Design

INTRODUCTION

The success of Vocational Technical Education (VTE) programmes is often measured by the employability of its graduates. This can be achieved when the vocational technical system of training is in congruence with industry demands and standards. Thus, the application of the same system of technical work practices in industries for vocational training. This effectively implies that vocational technical training should mirror the world of work. The same set of skills, patterns of training, equipment and machines as found in industries should be applied in vocational school-based training. An essential component of industries is the work environment. The Glassdoor team (2021) defined work environment as the elements that comprise the setting in which employees work and impact workers. It is the physical, social and psychological aspects of a work place. While some items that comprise work environment are quite obvious, such as machines, tools and equipment, others are more abstract. A work environment usually comprises a collection of diverse elements in relation to corporate conditions and job-specific conditions (Glassdoor team, 2021). For industries and workshops, there are emerging patterns of psychological work environment. They are mostly challenging and problem-based. The industrial worker is always expected to solve problems. The work environment is problem-based and revolves around solving problems.

The objective of vocational technical education among others is the acquisition of skills that ease transition-to-work. A successful school-to-work transition is when trainees possess the requisite skills demanded by industries even at entry level. The implication of this to training is that students are to be trained in the same environment and scenarios as they would find in the world of work. Hence, technical learning environment should become replica work environment as found in industries. Tsitsi (2018) commented that today's industries are characterized by dynamic work environment and the demand are on technologists to solve problems. This clearly depicts a challenging and problem solving work environment in industries for technologists. The requirement for today for VTE is that learning environment in should revolve around a problem-solving training method as found in industries and the world of work.

Mark (2013) defined learning environment as *the diverse physical locations, contexts, and cultures in which students learn*. Learning environment in Industrial Technical Education should mirror that of work environment. This has long been advocated by researchers in vocational technical education as vital for high-quality technical training (Okeke & Oranu, 2006). Accordingly, Elizabeth, *et al* (2006) found that a supportive and challenging learning environment is the keystone to a successful implementation of a problem solving work environment as found in industries. Successful problem solving instruction is to find the right balance between the challenge and support offered to learners. This will help create a problem-based learning environment (Caleb, 2019). The dilemma inherent in this principle is: How will a technical teacher structure learning to create sufficient challenge, but still provide enough support and what method of instruction could help create this leaning environment? One of such methods that can be used to develop these skills and create effective problem solving environment is the Problem-based Learning (PBL).

Problem-based Learning (PBL) is a learning method where real life occupational situations are introduced into the learning cycle and used to generate learning issues that mirrors work conditions obtainable in industries and for developing professional knowledge, skills and behaviours. It not only reproduces work conditions in the classroom and in schools, it makes acquisition of occupational and generic skills its focus. The theoretical underpinning for PBL is the constructivism theory which supports the idea of students constructing new knowledge while solving problems by themselves.

As a form of active learning, Problem-Based Learning encourages knowledge construction and integrates school learning with real life dynamics, where learners learn how to develop flexible knowledge and effective problem-solving skills, acquire intrinsic motivation, exchange ideas and collaborate. Through collaboration, learners are able to identify what they already know, what they need to know, as well as the way and the source of information they need to successfully reach to the solution of the problem. Instructors facilitate learning, by supporting, guiding and monitoring the learners' progress, building confidence, encouraging learners to actively participate and stretching their comprehension (Christopher,

2014). This method gives learners the opportunity to master their problem-solving, thinking, teamwork, communication, time management, research and computing skills. This supports the original idea of Boud(1985) that PBL acknowledges the experience base of learners as valid.

Finkle and Torp (1995) defined problem-based learning as a curriculum development and instructional system with a micro and macro components. At the micro level, it is used in curriculum development, where relevant problems are used to structure learning. At the macro or curriculum level, professional practice and situations drive the curriculum development. The curriculum design process involves an analysis of practical tasks and contents in which the students are expected to perform. The focus of the PBL curriculum is on what students should do and not on where they are (school). Thus, the PBL curriculum draws strength from real world tasks as found in occupations, so that a student can learn with the exact situations as would be found in the occupation even in the classroom. The sequencing in PBL curriculum design is in contrast to other methods.

At the micro level, PBL is deployed as an instructional method involving the use of facilitation and student centred learning methods for instruction. This consists of applying PBL instructional packages as the driving force behind student learning. PBL instructional packages are a competency-based curricula consisting of workplace-oriented and performance-based modules or units of competence that can be accumulated to a vocational qualification. PBL instructional design is a way of approaching vocational technical training that places primary emphasis on what a person can do as a result of training. It is concerned with training to industry specific standards rather than an individual's achievement relative to others in the group.

The PBL curricula aims at preparing learners more effectively for real workplaces, which means that the acquisition of competencies takes into account the requirements of companies and industries. Conway and Little (2000) advocated that both the micro and macro application of PBL requires practice situations to drive student learning. However, the focus on educational outcomes should go beyond specific concepts of learning, to show inter-relatedness of concepts essential for troubleshooting technical problems as well as carrying out installation, repairs and maintenance.

The PBL approach by utilizing real world work situations according to Savin-Baden (2000) provides students with greater challenge and motivation to engage in course work. This is achieved through activating prior knowledge, increasing understanding of basic science/technological concepts and organizing compartmental conceptual knowledge to construct an elaborate and well-integrated knowledge structure. This helps to foster learning and transfer knowledge from the theoretical to the practical work context as is the case in industrial technology education. In the case of industrial technical education, real life (authentic) scenarios offer the students the opportunity to learn different areas in their chosen occupational field in context. Most programmes and institutions have their own version of PBL, however, the core thrust is the facilitation of students' self-directed learning while encouraging contextual learning. In most PBL applications, especially in the medical field, the learning takes place through a series of 'real-life' circumstances in which the students learn the several aspects of medicine in context. Students are exposed to each topic as well as each concept many times and from different angles and with increasing complexity. Gradually, 'paper' scenarios give way to clinical incidents as the students progress. The overall objective is to facilitate integrated learning within concepts and between concepts and the attachment of new learning into Long Term Memory (LTM). As the knowledge and understanding base grows, the frequent revisitation with more complex ideas allows a flexible network of ideas to be established. One of the basic tools in this learning process is the Concept Map. (Draneni, 2018).

Evidence from Savin-Baden (2000) indicated that by analyzing a problem, students' prior knowledge is triggered, which helps them to build a theory about the problem and enables the student to understand a variety of aspects that are relevant for their professional career.

As Zanolli, Boshuizen and De Grave(2002) pointed out, inadequate problem exploration and insufficient structuring of prior knowledge may result in unclear or ambiguous learning objectives. Thus, the problem, which is the essential ingredient in PBL tutorial, should be explored from all angles, fully and positioned in the mind of the learner based on previous knowledge. Such a positioning would reveal to the learner,

what they already know about the problem and put in context, what they need to know (learning issues) to solve the problem.

Gijbels, *et al* (2005) averred that PBL is more effective when linkages are made between focal concepts rather than understanding concepts in isolation. This notion led to researchers incorporating concept mapping (CM) into the PBL process. Concept mapping according to Hay(2007) seems to be a suited tool to help students visualize prior knowledge structures and to advance meaningful learning. Schmidt, Rotgans and Yew (2011) defined concept mapping (CM) as a schematic device for organizing and representing a set of concepts embedded in a framework of propositions, by graphically illustrating the complex processes or relationships among relevant concepts within a given subject domain.

Students are encouraged to use the maps for three related purposes: to plan their work, to make explicit their own mental network and to prepare materials for later formal assessment. The maps are not themselves assessed, but they are aids for revision and inter-linking of knowledge (Alex & Kevin, 2006). CM applied as a learning strategy in PBL, supports learners' process of externalizing their thinking in a visual/verbal form with the aim of improving students' understanding and organization of declarative and procedural knowledge. This enables the students to abstract essential information, relate ideas and concepts as well as representing them in a structured manner that shows linkages and progression. The result is a concept map where concepts are enclosed in nodes and attached by links.

Concept maps often start with a key concept. Students then link concepts using lines and linking words to form statements and propositions (Novak & Cañas, 2006). Hierarchies form an essential part of a CM. to show the hierarchy, the more general concepts are placed at the top and more specific concepts come below and extend outward. A group of related tasks form a skill, thus, sequencing of a series of related tasks and concept-links in a hierarchical chain represents a domain of knowledge. It must be noted that in industrial technical education, the specific concepts are often technical processes and tasks to be completed. The relationship between different domains of knowledge is indicated by cross-links, which are also connected using labeled lines, describing the nature of the relationship. Optionally, examples may be added and linked to the related concept in the most subordinate position on the map.

Central to the successful use of PBL methodologies is the preparation of teachers for the facilitator role as asserted by Maudsley (1999). PBL requires the teacher to function, in the main, as a facilitator rather than a transmitter of information. Teaching approaches of this nature pay due respect to the contributions of both teacher and student and result in a shared learning process. The leader of a PBL programme acts as a facilitator and trainer rather than a teacher, using their expertise not primarily to transmit facts, but to provide tasks, encouragement, guidance and support, as the participants tackle the problems they have identified. The skill of PBL facilitation according to Maudsley (1999, p. 658) is that of knowing when to provide assistance to the group, be it suggesting useful resources they might like to consider or interjecting with thought provoking comments to guide the breadth and depth of learning, without necessarily imparting facts. Instruction becomes interaction; the role of the teacher thus becomes that of facilitator rather than primary sources of knowledge. There is considerable research evidence in support of the educational value of facilitation in PBL (Albanese & Mitchell 1993).

Facilitation is a goal-orientated dynamic process in which participants work together in an atmosphere of genuine mutual respect, in order to learn through critical reflection. (Burrows 1997, p.401). Within PBL tutorials, educational facilitation encompasses guiding learners through their own discovery without teaching in the traditional sense (Biley & Smith 1999). Facilitation involves interaction between teachers and students that involves questioning, dialogue, feedback and creating a structured environment to promote inquiry, exploration, discovery and engagement in a PBL class.

The PBL facilitator 'negotiates new understandings, utilizes effective interpersonal skills, and promotes open discussion in class' (Creedy 1993, p.212). Wilkerson and Hundert (1997) assert that the PBL facilitator may need to redefine their relationship with students and with programme content. To this end, the PBL facilitator will release control of programme content and the learning process and form a learning partnership with students, trusting them to accomplish programme outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Problem-based learning has received considerable attention in medicine and is increasingly being applied in engineering and technology discipline. The effectiveness of PBL in engineering may not be in doubt. What is challenging however, is the extent of awareness and application among vocational technical educators. Instruction in industrial technical education has been dominated by demonstration method. However, a hybrid model involving PBL and demonstration method is gaining attention among instructors. Given the increasing acceptance of PBL as an essential instructional strategy in technical education, the eagerness to implement PBL is hindered by the skills level of technical teachers' in application of PBL instructional design and delivery principles, of which concept mapping forms an integral part.

The problem with implementing and integrating PBL into vocational technical education is that the technical instructors are not conversant with PBL methodology neither are they aware of the instructional principles underlying the use of PBL for instruction in VTE. For a discipline that has become synonymous with demonstration method, the adoption of a new method has been an uphill task. Thus, there is need to develop the competencies of VTE instructors on the implementation of problem-based learning in vocational technical educators.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to develop a template for integrating concept maps into problem-based learning in technical education. Specifically, the study seeks to

1. Develop guidelines for constructing concept maps
2. Develop a template for applying concept maps in problem-based learning scenarios
3. Develop a template for facilitating learning by technical teachers

Research Questions

The following research questions are stated for the study

1. What are the guidelines for constructing concept maps?
2. What is the template for applying concept maps in problem-based learning scenarios?
3. What is the guideline for facilitating learning in PBL by technical teachers

METHOD

Instrumentation research design was employed in the study. Instrumentation design is appropriate for use when introducing new procedures, technologies or instrument for educational practices (Gay, 1996). The area of the study was South-South zone of Nigeria comprising, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers States. The population of the study is 54 respondents, comprising lecturers in the technical/industrial education unit as experts. The sample size for lecturers used in the study is 46. This was arrived at using Taro Yamanne's formula. The stratified random sampling technique was employed for the sampling of the universities, with each university taken as a stratum. Thereafter, simple random sampling technique was employed to sample lecturers from the participating universities. The Universities were Delta State University(7), University of Uyo (6), Rivers State University (7), Cross River State University of Technology(6), Niger Delta University(5), Edo State University(5), University of Benin(5), Rivers State University of Education(5).

Qualitative and quantitative data was collected for the study. Data for the study were collected using questionnaire, focus group discussion and the Delphi technique. This went on for a period of 90 working days. The developed instrument was then presented to experts in the Delphi technique, who screened the items to ensure that they served as inputs to education. Seven experts were involved in the Delphi process of validation. Content validation was carried out through the Delphi process. Content experts reviewed the items for inclusion in the develop template. The inputs of the experts was used to build the final version of the PBL-concept map template. The data generated from administering the instrument to the experts was analysed using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR). The developed template for problem selection and PBL implementation was then pretested through a pilot test. This was conducted at the University of Uyo. Student-teachers were asked to rate the training they just received. Cronbach Alpha

was then used for determining the internal consistency of the developed template. This gave a coefficient index of 0.87. Based on the high reliability coefficient, the instrument was deemed fit for the study.

PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS

Research Question One: *What are the guidelines for constructing a concept map?*

Table 1: Template for Designing Concept Maps for technical teachers

S/N	Concept map creation phases	Key indicators	Analysis	
1	Brainstorming Phase	Critical Thinking	From memory, identify facts, ideas, concepts, themes, queries that come to mind when thinking about this topic	
		Group discussion	Make a list of these items	
		Listing steps	write down everything that anybody in your group thinks is important and avoid discussing how important the item is	
2	Organizing Phase	Establish a main concept	Spread out the concepts so it can be read easily read	Try to group items to emphasize hierarchies
		Organize the ideas into categories	create groups and sub-groups of related items	Identify terms that represent those higher categories and add them.
		organization may change as you continue to read and add more information.	Feel free to rearrange items and introduce new items that you omitted initially.	Note that some concepts will fall into multiple groupings. This will become important later.
3	Layout Phase	Identify related concepts	It is recommended to start a concept map from the top and develop it downward, although one can put down the topic at the center and expand it outwards. Either way make sure that the central topic stands out from the rest (use a bigger node, a different color etc.).	try to come up with an arrangement (layout) that best represents your collective understanding of the interrelationships and connections among groupings.
		Organize shapes and lines	Use a consistent hierarchy in which the most important concepts are in the center or at the top	Within sub-grouping, place closely related items near to each other.
			Feel free to rearrange things at any time during this phase	Think in terms of connecting the items in a simple sentence that shows the relationship between them
4	Linking Phase	Use links as propositions	Use lines with arrows to connect and show the relationship between connected items	Write a word or short phrase by each arrow to specify the relationship or activity to

		Concepts should be represented in a hierarchical fashion with the most inclusive, most general concepts at the top of the map and the more specific, less general concepts arranged hierarchically below.	Many arrows can originate or terminate on particularly important concepts	be carried out Scrutinize what you have created to make sure that you haven't missed anything and that the relationships you have identified make sense
		Concept maps should be built with a context in mind. E.g. one can construct concept maps with reference to a focus question		
5	<i>Finalizing the Concept Map</i>	Accuracy and Thoroughness. Are the concepts and relationships correct? Are important concepts missing? Are any misconceptions apparent?	After your group has agreed on an arrangement of items that conveys your understanding, you need to convert the concept map into a permanent form that others can view and discuss	
		Organization. Was the concept map laid out in a way that higher order relationships are apparent and easy to follow?	Be creative communicating your understanding.	
		Creativity- Are there unusual elements that aid communication or stimulate interest without being distracting?	Give your concept map a title	
		Appearance. Was the assignment done with care showing attention to details such as spelling and penmanship? Is it neat and orderly or is it chaotic and		

		messy?		
6	Key Characteristics of a Concept Map	Nodes	Nodes are the circles or the boxes that are used to represent a concept or an idea.	Nodes may vary in size, according to their hierarchy on the map; for example, more general nodes at the top of the map may be bigger than the more specific nodes that follow them.
		Cross-Links	Concept maps consist of concepts in different domains. And the relationships between these different domains of knowledge are shown with cross-links.	
		Linking Words	Or linking phrases if it contains more than a word. These describe the type of relationship between the two concepts and appear on the line connecting them.	
		Hierarchical Structure	Usually, concept maps are organized hierarchically. This means the most general and inclusive concepts are placed at the top of the map. Those that are more specific are positioned below them. Accordingly, hierarchical concept maps are read from top to bottom	However, the structure of a concept map is not limited to this structure, it could take a free-form approach too – starting from the center and spreading outwards
		Propositional Structure	A concept map illustrates a set of meaningful propositions about a topic.	Every two concepts (in some cases more than two,) along with the linking phrases, form a meaningful sentence, otherwise known as a proposition.
		Focus Question	Generally, a concept map should be woven around a focus question, which is the problem or the issue the concept map seeks to resolve. The better the focus question, the richer the concept map will be.	

Table 1 shows the developed template for designing concept maps. This template is useful for both instructors and learners alike. The template identifies the key characteristics of a concept map. The template also identifies the concept map creation phases to include brainstorming phase, organizing phase, layout phase and linking phase. The template also identified key indicators in each phase as well as activities and steps required for constructing concept maps.

Research Question 2: *What are the guidelines for integrating concept maps into problem-based learning tutorials?*

Table 2: Guidelines for integrating concept maps into problem-based learning

S/N	Learning Steps using PBL	Concept map application in PBL		Students' specific CM-PBL activities
1	Define the problem	Pick a Topic-	The first step is to identify a topic you need to study with your concept map. This could be an idea, a question or an issue.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore problems • Identify facts • Generate ideas • Discuss prior and current knowledge • Identify learning issues
2	Understand the problem	Do a Quick Brainstorm	What are the facts, ideas, concepts, themes, queries that come to mind when thinking about this topic? Note these down as you brainstorm around the topic you have selected.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss learning issues • Discuss learning resources • Theme based session • Self directed learning • Practical sessions • Review problem and share new knowledge • Evaluate performance • Consolidate and integrate learning • Prepare product
3	Identify the problem	Focus Question	Identify a focus question that addresses the problem, issues, or knowledge domain you wish to map.	
4	Define the steps of solving the problem	Start to Draw the Map	start a concept map from the top and develop it downward, although one can put down the topic at the center and expand it outwards.	
5	Analyse the problem	connect what you have brainstormed to the central topic and to each other. Remember, the more important the idea, the closer it should be to the top or the center	Rank order the concepts by placing the broadest and most inclusive idea at the top of the map..	
6	Identify content	Connect the Concepts	Identify 10 to 20 concepts	

			that are pertinent to the question and list these. Concept labels should be a single word, or at most two or three words	
3 77	Continue research	Work down the list and add more concepts as needed.	Begin to build your map by placing the most inclusive, most general concept(s) at the top. Usually there will be only one, two, or three most general concepts at the top of the map.	Next, select the two, three, or four sub-concepts to place under each general concept.
8	Synthesise knowledge	Link concepts identify connections.	Connect the concepts by lines. Label the lines with one or a few linking words. The linking words should define the relationship between the two concepts so that it reads as a valid statement or proposition. put down the linking words or phrases to indicate the relationship between the two concepts you are linking	Once the direct connections between concepts have been identified, look for crosslinks that link together concepts from different areas or domains and label these lines. Use lines or arrows on the map to represent how ideas are connected to one another, a particular category, and/or the main concept
9	Conclude and evaluate the answer	Rework the structure of your map, which may include adding, subtracting, or changing super-ordinate concepts.	Scrutinize what you have created to make sure that you haven't missed anything and that the relationships you have identified make sense	Concept maps could be made in many different forms for the same set of concepts. There is no one way to draw a concept map. As your understanding of relationships between concepts changes, so will your maps.
10	Present and evaluate students' work	The tutor acts as a guide and facilitator to the participants rather than a subject matter expert conducting death by power point	Tutor Marked Assignment (Summative Assessment)	Skills Based Practical Exercises (Summative Assessment). PBL Tutorial Performance Formative Assessment

Table 2 shows the guidelines for integrating concept maps into problem-based learning. The result of the content analysis reveals the guidelines for integrating CM into the PBL tutorial process. The template is designed in three stages; the first stage is the learning steps in PBL. Stage two describes the process of integrating CM into PBL tutorial, with a step by step approach. Stage three lists specific activities by students and instructors in the PBL process.

Research Question 3: *What is the guideline for facilitating learning in PBL by technical teachers?*

Table 2: Guidelines for facilitating learning in PBL by technical teachers

Issues	Content	Guided Instruction Environment		Emphasis Covered
		Teacher activity	Pupils Activity	
Guidelines for instructional scaffolds	<p>1.Intentionality- The task has a clear overall purpose driving any separate activity that may contribute to the whole</p> <p>2.Appropriateness: Instructional tasks pose problems that can be solved with help but which students could not successfully complete on their own.</p> <p>3.Structure: Modeling and questioning activities are structured around a model of appropriate approaches to the task and lead to a natural sequence of thought and language.</p> <p>4.Collaboration: The teacher's response to student work recasts and expands upon the students' efforts without rejecting what they have accomplished on their own. The teacher's primary role is collaborative rather than evaluative.</p> <p>5. Internalization: External scaffolding for the activity is gradually withdrawn as the patterns are internalized by the students.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pre-engage the students and the curriculum. 2. Establish a shared goal. 3. Actively diagnose students' needs and understandings. 4. Provide tailored assistance. 5. Maintain pursuit of the goal. 6. Give feedback 7. Control for frustration and risk 8. Present information in a just-in-time approach 9. Assist internalization, independence, and generalization to other contexts 	<p>Tutees express new ideas, model their thinking, work together and benefit from knowledge and skills of other peers</p>	<p>Collaborative and critical thinking skills</p>
essential elements of Guided instruction	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Allow time for class discussion of the problem. 2. Assign students to groups by an arbitrary method. 3. Scaffold 4. Build upon the lesson. 5. Introduce a problem at the beginning of the class, or during the previous class, with a very brief "mini-lecture." 6. Generate interest and controversy and cause the learner to ask questions. 7. Effective tutoring 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Introduce a problem at the beginning of the class, or during the previous class, with a very brief "mini-lecture." (2) The teacher is open to new ideas. (3) The teacher encourages freedom to express new ideas by students (4) Provides sufficient resources for instruction (5) Creates idea time in class (6) The 	<p>The tutees demonstrate group-processing skill, ask questions to clarify misunderstanding.</p> <p>The tutees reasoning out answers, post questions, make connections between concepts</p> <p>The tutees show comprehensive understanding of and respect for one another as</p>	<p>Creative, Collaborative, problem solving and work skills.</p>

		teachers uses playfulness and humour in class (7) The teacher encourages debates in class (8) The teacher validates the students by supporting their ideas (9) Provide support to students by offering information in just-in-time approach Fading. The final theoretical feature requires that the teacher fade the support provided to the learner(s).	well as interaction and interactivity	
Evaluation		1. Construction of Knowledge/ Individual accountability. 2. Challenging work is given to students 3. The teacher asks question and gives class work	The tutees articulate their ideas, respond to their peer-mate points, develop technical skills and demonstrate creative and analytical skills as well as other soft skills	Collaborative learning skills/ work
Summary	The tutor summarizes the lesson based on the objectives.	Reward and recognition	Students celebrate their success	

Table 3 shows the summary of the template for the use of guided instructional strategy in a problem-based learning environment. The teacher is expected to familiarise with the tenets of scaffolding for effective mentoring of students in a PBL environment. Some of the tasks in the guidelines for guided instruction as identified by the template are Allow time for class discussion of the problem; assign students to groups by an arbitrary method; Scaffold; build upon the lesson; introduce a problem at the beginning of the class, or during the previous class, with a very brief “mini-lecture”; generate interest and controversy and cause the learner to ask questions and effective tutoring.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Concept maps are tools for organizing and representing knowledge. A concept map illustrates a set of meaningful propositions about a topic. Concept mapping is introduced to show techniques by which students can be assessed, as well as a means by which instructors can convey information to their students. The study adopted the concept development stages identified by Novak and Musonda (1991) which itemized steps in integrating CM into PBL. The identified CM steps and processes for applying

concept maps in PBL is corroborated by David, Lee and Andrew (2003) which developed CM-PBL integration steps as 1) determine the topic or domain of interest to be modeled, 2) write that term (concept) in the middle of a sheet of paper, 3) think of related concepts to that initial one and begin writing them down on the paper near the first term, 4) connect related concepts with lines, and 5) keep adding more concepts and relationship lines to the map as it grows. Keeping in mind there is no minimum or maximum size to a concept map – the size will depend on the understanding of the topic and the concepts the subject relates to the initial term. One outcome of these visual representations is a focus upon developing and recalling relevant associations rather than memorizing concepts recorded in a more linear fashion.

The findings of the study show the facilitation skills needed for implementing a problem-based learning environment. The teacher is expected to familiarize with the tenets of scaffolding for effective mentoring of students in a PBL environment. Some of the tasks in the guidelines for guided instruction as identified by the template are Allow time for class discussion of the problem; assign students to groups by an arbitrary method; Scaffold; build upon the lesson. The findings of the study is corroborated by (McKenzie, 2000) which found that the major responsibilities of the teacher during the modeling stage of cognitive apprenticeship are structuring situations of expert practice and demonstrating the expert's thinking process in a manner that does not overwhelm students. The goal of this stage is to build mental models of experts' cognitive processes so that students can eventually work on their own. Scaffolds are developed in order to assist student with a difficult task. The key is that the assistance is planned in advance. Since it involves a process that cannot be directly observed and experienced, cognitive modelling according to Holton, *et al.*, (2006), requires more sophisticated planning to apply in classrooms than does modelling of physical performance. The modelling of cognitive processes requires the following: modelling an expert's performance; Externalizing internal/cognitive processes (verbalizing thought processes); encouraging students to think like experts and treating them as experts; modelling the performance in different contexts and demonstrating how to cope with difficulties

CONCLUSION

Concepts and propositions are the building blocks for knowledge in any domain. Mapping concepts, ideas, class notes and plans is an effective technique to quickly present information in a visual way. Reviewing content on the concept map helps identify missing elements and redundant or unnecessary information to ensure the information presented is a meaningful whole. It is concluded that the developed template is suitable for use by technical education instructors and students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made

1. The developed template for concept map integration into PBL tutorial should be adopted by the teacher in the design of PBL instruction in technical education.
2. Technical instructors should review the completed concept map by asking the question, "Does this make sense to me?" remembering that concept maps can be as unique as the individual who created it.
3. The technical teacher should explore the use of Concept maps as a helpful tool for use in representing material to the class.
4. Teachers should explore the use of PBL and demonstration hybrid methods of instruction in technical education.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful for the opportunity to present findings from their research "A Train-the-Trainer Approach for Implementing Problem-Based Learning Environment in Vocational Technical Education"

With full support from the Tertiary Education Fund (TETFUND) Nigeria, which provided funding for this project with Reference number TETF/DR&D/CE/AKWA-IBOM/IBR/2023/Vol.1 and TETFUND/IBR/COE/AFAHA-NSIT/PR/079

REFERENCES

- Alex H. & Kevin H. (2006). Concept mapping in problem based learning: a cautionary tale. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 7 (2), 84-95.
- Caleb, E.E.(2019). Development and Validation of Training Modules for Effective Implementation of Problem-based Learning in Electrical/Electronics Technology Programme in South-South Nigeria. unpublished Ph.D Dissertation, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Christopher, P.(2014). Instructional design models and theories: problem-based learning. Retrieved from <https://elearningindustry.com/problem-based-learning> on 12/12/2018.
- David, T., Lee, A. & Andrew, U. (2003). Concept maps for teaching and assessment. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 12, 396-405.
- De Simone, C., Richard F. & McEwen, L. (2001). Supporting the Learning Process with Collaborative Concept Mapping Using Computer-Based Communication Tools and Processes. *Educational Research and Evaluation* 7(2 -3):263-283.
- Draneni, N.(2018). Using concept mapping through problem-based learning to facilitate lifelong knowledge of risk factors for cardiovascular diseases: case university of Algiers. Being a paper presented at the PBL for the next generation: blending active learning, technology and social justice. International conference, Santa Clara, California, USA, 16-19 February, 2018.
- Elizabeth, G., Jocelyn D., & Simon, F. (2006). *Principles of learning: Advancing performance in today's workplace*. The Forum Corporation of North America. Paper No FOR5102.
- Gay, L. R. (1996). *Educational research .competences, for analysis and application*. (5th Ed.). Merrill, Prentice Hall.
- Gijbels, D., Dochy, F., Van den Bossche, P., & Segers, M. (2005). Effects of problem-based learning: A meta-analysis from the angle of assessment. *Review of Educational Research*, 75(1), 27-61. doi:10.3102/00346543075001027
- Hay, D. B. (2007). Using concept maps to measure deep, surface and non-learning outcomes. *Studies in Higher Education*, 32(1), 39-57. doi:10.1080/03075070601099432
- Holton, Derek, and Clark, David (2006). Scaffolding and Metacognition. *International Journal Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 37, 127-143.
- Mark, O. (2013). *Modern learning environment* . CORE Education white paper, New Zealand.
- McKenzie, J. (2000). Scaffolding for Success. Beyond Technology, Questioning, Research and the Information Literate School Community. Retrieved from <http://fno.org/dec99/scaffold.html> on 21 February, 2015.
- Novak, D. J., & Cañas, A. J. (2006). The theory underlying concept maps and how to construct them. Technical Report IHMC CmapTools 2006-01. Florida Institute for Human and Machine Cognition. Retrieved from <http://cmap.ihmc.us/Publications/ResearchPapers/TheoryUnderlyingConceptMaps.pdf>
- Novak, J.D. & D. Musonda (1991). A twelve-year longitudinal study of science concept learning. *American Educational Research Journal* 28(1), 117-153.
- Okeke, C. & Oranu, N. (2006). *Principles and practice in the management of industrial vocational and technical workshop*. Onitsha, AN: Base 5 Publishers.
- Savin-Baden, M. (2000). Problem-based learning in higher education: Untold stories. Buckingham: Society for Research into Higher Education (SRHE) & Open University Press
- Schmidt, H.G., Rotgans, J.I. & Yew, E.H.(2011). The process of problem-based learning: what works and why. *Medical Education*, 45(8),792–806.
- Tsitsi, M. (2018). *Dynamic Strategy in a Turbulent Business Environment*. IntechOpen, DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.81250. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/dynamic-strategy-in-a-turbulent-business-environment>.
- Zanolli, M. B., Boshuizen, H. P. A., & De Grave, W. S. (2002). Students' and tutors' perceptions of problems in PBL tutorial groups at a Brazilian medical school. *Education for Health*, 15(2), 189-201.